

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STOCK, FOREIGN EXCHANGE AND COMMODITY MARKETS –A STUDY IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT

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Abstract

During the last three decades, the financial markets across the globe have become highly integrated with each other as well as with the markets in other countries. This inter-relationship has thrown open lot of investment opportunities, but, has also resulted in increased risk. The same applies to Indian markets too. In the light of increased integration between various markets, the current study attempts to analyse three major markets in India, namely, the stock market, foreign exchange market and commodity market. Nifty, the fifty share index of National Stock Exchange is considered to represent the stock market, while exchange rate of US Dollar is used for representing the foreign exchange market and gold and crude oil are included from the commodity market. Data related to these markets were collected for a period of ten years from 2008 to 2018. Annual rates of returns, daily returns, and volatility of returns as well as Granger Causality test were applied to draw conclusions about the nature of relationship among the markets. It was found that stock market and gold provided comparatively better returns, crude oil showed highest level of risk. Unidirectional causality was found between stock market and foreign exchange market, gold and foreign exchange, foreign exchange and crude oil, stock market and crude oil and gold and crude oil. No signs of causality were seen between stock market and gold.

Keywords: Market inter-relationship, Returns, Volatility, Granger causality, Foreign exchange, Commodity market.

1. INTRODUCTION

The financial markets world-wide attracted a lot of attention over the last two decades for various reasons. While on one side there were many turbulences triggered by events such as US subprime crisis, the markets also threw open various new investment opportunities. The most important development that took place during this period is the integration of various markets and markets across countries. Today no market can be seen as protected from the shocks emerging from other markets. Indian markets are no exception to this. While Indian markets remained largely aloof before the country embarked on its globalization drive three decades ago. Through leaps and bounds, the market has grown manifold during this period. Stock market was considered to be the only strong arm of financial markets for a long time and investment in gold was mostly in terms of jewelry.

But, over the last two decades the spectrum of investment expanded a lot in the country, with people looking at various classes of assets like foreign exchange, gold and other commodities. Thus, along with the stock market, the foreign exchange market and commodity market have emerged as active markets in the country. In this context, the current study attempts to examine the performance of

these markets as well as to analyse the inter-relationships and influences they have on each other.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

- To analyse the rates of returns and risks of investment in stock market, foreign exchange market and commodity markets in India.
- To study the inter-relationship among these markets and examine the flow of causality.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A good number of studies have been conducted to observe the effects of macroeconomic variables such as gold, crude oil, foreign exchange and index. A brief review of some of the significant studies is presented below.

Fama (1981)⁽²⁾ explored the relationship between stock returns, real activity, inflation and money, which showed that stock returns and inflation rates are most strongly related (opposite signs) to measures of future real activity. Büyüksalvarci and Abdioglu (2010)⁽¹⁾ studied the causal relationship between stock prices and macroeconomic variables such as foreign exchange rate, gold price, broad

money supply, industrial production index and consumer price index in Turkey for a period of 9 years using the long run Granger non-causality test. The results conclude that there is a unidirectional long-run causality from stock price to macro variables for Turkey.

Sujit and Kumar (2011)⁽⁸⁾ tested the dynamic relationship among gold price, exchange rate, stock returns and oil price. Vector Autoregression (VAR) is used to examine the impact of oil price, exchange rate and stock market on gold price. The results show that exchange rate is highly affected by changes in other variables, but, stock market has fewer roles in affecting the exchange rate. Among the two models tested in the study, one model suggests that there is a weak long term relationship among the variables. Ray (2012)⁽⁶⁾ examines whether there exists any causal linkage between stock prices and macroeconomic variables designing multiple regression model and granger causality test.

Patel (2012)⁽⁵⁾ investigates the effect of macroeconomic determinants on the performance of the Indian Stock Market using monthly data. Eight macroeconomic variables, namely, Interest Rate, Inflation, Exchange Rate, Index of Industrial Production, Money Supply, Gold Price, Silver Price & Oil Price, and two stock market indices namely Sensex and S&P CNX Nifty are considered for the study.

Jain and Ghosh (2012)⁽⁴⁾ examined the long-term equilibrium relationship between oil prices, exchange rate and the prices of precious metals. The tests results in co integration among the variables when exchange rate and gold are dependent variables. The study also used a Granger causality test which indicates that exchange rate causes all the variables and some relationships between the precious metals and oil exist. Sahu et al (2014)⁽⁷⁾ investigated the dynamic relationships between oil price shocks and Indian stock market. To demonstrate the long-run and short-run relationship between them Johansen's co integration test, vector error correction model (VECM), Granger causality test, impulse response functions (IRFs) and variance decompositions (VDCs) test were applied. The co integration result indicates the existence of long-term relationship and the Granger causality test results of showed that no short-run causality between the variable exists.

Ingalhalli et al (2016)⁽³⁾ studied the causal relationship between oil, gold, forex and stock markets. The study employed Granger causality test. The results of the study indicate the existence of unidirectional relationship among the variables and also reveal that oil prices contribute towards development and forecasting of exchange rate and gold prices, whereas fluctuations in oil prices are granger caused by Sensex.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The literature reviewed above suggests mixed results with no clear evidence on the influence of different markets on

the other. In this context, the current study attempts to analyse the rates of returns and the risk involved in the stock market, foreign exchange market and commodity market (represented by gold and crude oil) in India. Attempt is also made to understand the inter-relationships among these markets and to examine the flow of causality between them.

3.1 Data Descriptions

The study considers data for a period of ten years from 01-04-2008 to 31-03-2018. The stock market is represented by Nifty, the fifty stock index of National Stock Exchange (NSE), Mumbai. Daily closing values of Nifty for the period of study are collected from the website of NSE. The foreign exchange market is represented by the exchange rate between US Dollar and Indian Rupee. Daily closing prices of Dollar are collected from the website of Reserve Bank of India (RBI). The commodity market is represented by two leading commodities, gold and crude oil. Daily spot prices of these commodities are collected from the website of Multi Commodity Exchange (MCX), Mumbai. The reference market for gold is Ahmedabad and for crude oil, it is Mumbai.

3.2 Scheme of Analysis

The data analysis is classified into three sections, analysis of annual rates of returns, analysis of daily rates of returns and the relationship between the daily rates of returns of the three markets. The scheme of analysis followed in the study is as detailed below:

- Annual Returns:** Annual rates of returns and standard deviations are computed for the ten year period for all the four variables, viz. Nifty, US Dollar, Gold and Crude Oil using the formula $[P_E - P_B]/P_B$, where P_E is the price on the last trading day of the year and P_B the price on the first trading day of the year. Comparison of rates of returns and standard deviations is done by summarising the results.
- Daily Returns and Risk:** The rest of the study is based on daily rates of returns of the variables. Daily closing values of the variables are transformed by computing their natural logarithms. The daily rates of returns are computed as the first difference of the series of natural logarithms. In other words, the rate of return on a particular day is defined as $[\ln(P_t) - \ln(P_{t-1})]$, where P_t represents price on day 't' and P_{t-1} represents price on the previous (t-1) day. Average daily returns and their standard deviations are computed for all the variables.
- Descriptive Statistics:** Descriptive statistics such as mean, median, maximum, minimum, skewness and kurtosis for the daily rates of returns are reported for the ten year period. The normality of the data series are tested using Jarque-Bera (JB) statistic.
- Unit Root Test:** The data series are tested for the stationarity (unit root property) using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test. ADF test is performed at

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the level data (natural logarithms of prices) and at first difference (the daily rates of returns). Stationarity of data is a prerequisite for the causality test used in the study.

e) **Granger Causality Test:** Granger Causality test is used to analyse the inter-relationship between each pair of the variables. Granger causality test explains how much of the current value of a variable (y) can be explained using its own lagged values and lagged values of another variable (x). Two lags of each variable are used in the current study. The Granger causality test uses the following two regression equations

$$y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 y_{t-1} + \alpha_2 y_{t-2} + \beta_1 x_{t-1} + \beta_2 x_{t-2} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$x_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x_{t-1} + \alpha_2 x_{t-2} + \beta_1 y_{t-1} + \beta_2 y_{t-2} + u_t \quad (2)$$

The test reports F-Statistic for the joint hypothesis that $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 0$. Hence, the null hypothesis for equation (1) is that 'x does not Granger Cause y' and the same for equation (2) is that 'y does not Granger Cause x'. Pair wise test results are reported in the study.

4. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Annual Returns and Risk: The trends of all the variables are presented in Figure 1 (Nifty, Gold and crude oil prices are on the primary y-axis and the Dollar value is presented on the secondary y-axis). It can be seen that all the variables, except crude oil price, exhibited upward trend during the 10 year period. The 2018 crude prices remained almost at the same level as 2008, but with wide fluctuations during the intermittent period.

Figure 1: Nifty, Gold, Crude Oil and US Dollar Prices (2008-18)

The annual rates of returns and their standard deviations are presented in Table 1. It can be observed that while Nifty (10.57%) and gold (10.78%) offered high average returns during the period, Dollar (5.44%) and crude oil (5.53%) offered lower returns. Nifty offered the highest returns (71.52%) in 2009-10 and the lowest (-36.26%) in 2008-09. Gold offered the highest return (33.09%) in

2011-12 and the lowest (-7.85%) in 2014-15. The highest returns for crude oil and Dollar were 53.42% and 27.47% in 2009-10 and 2008-09 respectively; whereas the lowest returns were -50.06% and -11.40% in 2014-15 and 2009-10 respectively. It can be seen that the volatility of most of these prices were high during 2008-10, which coincided with the subprime crisis and global meltdown. The relationship between Nifty and Dollar during this period is worth mentioning. While Nifty lost heavily in 2008-09 and bounced back the next year, the opposite was true with Dollar, which went up in 2008-09 and fell in the subsequent year. This was the direct impact of subprime crisis, which made the Dollar dearer in 2008-09 when the crisis was at its peak and pushed the stock markets down. When the stock market ultimately recovered from the shock during the next year, Dollar value took a beating.

Table 1: Annual Rates of Returns

	Nifty	US Dollar	Gold	Crude Oil
2008-09	-36.26%	27.47%	29.26%	-38.21%
2009-10	71.52%	-11.40%	7.63%	53.42%
2010-11	10.27%	-1.09%	27.09%	21.98%
2011-12	-9.11%	14.57%	33.09%	10.33%
2012-13	6.86%	6.32%	5.68%	-0.53%
2013-14	17.53%	10.50%	-3.07%	15.54%
2014-15	26.33%	4.14%	-7.85%	-50.06%
2015-16	-9.87%	5.98%	11.12%	-14.57%
2016-17	18.94%	-2.25%	-1.90%	28.55%
2017-18	9.48%	0.21%	6.80%	28.86%
Average	10.57%	5.44%	10.78%	5.53%
Standard Deviation	28.08%	10.59%	14.36%	31.98%

In terms of standard deviation, it can be seen from Table 1, that Nifty and crude prices showed the wide variations in annual rates of returns, and thus were more risky compared to gold and Dollar. US Dollar showed the lowest level of risk in terms of standard deviation of the annual returns during 2008-2018.

Daily Rates of Returns: The daily rates of returns as the first difference of logs of variables was computed for the ten year period. There were 2473 observations for each variable. The descriptive statistics of daily returns is given in Table 2.

It can be observed from Table-2 that all the variables have close to zero daily returns with non-zero standard deviation. Crude oil exhibited maximum risk in terms of standard deviation. A look at the maximum and minimum returns also indicates that the highest values (17.48% and -15.28%) are shown by crude oil. The lowest standard deviation is exhibited by Dollar. It can be observed that all the variables are positively skewed. The kurtosis of above 3 indicates that all the return series are leptokurtic with high peaks, values concentrated around

mean and fat tails. The normality of the daily returns is tested with the Jarque-Bera (JB) statistic. It can be observed that the JB statistic is significant at 5% level for all data series, indicating that the series are not distributed normally. The daily returns on assets are expected to show mean return of zero with non-zero standard deviation. Further, they are mostly leptokurtic, asymmetric and not distributed normally. It can be seen that the daily rates of returns on Nifty, Dollar, gold and crude oil are exhibiting the same properties.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics-Daily Returns

	Nifty	US Dollar	Gold	Crude Oil
Mean (%)	0.03060	0.01970	0.03910	0.00222
Median (%)	0.04620	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000
Maximum (%)	16.33430	4.02000	10.44980	17.48350
Minimum (%)	-13.01420	-3.00650	-8.65760	15.28040
Standard Deviation (%)	1.35660	0.51720	0.99950	2.39900
Skewness	0.22809	0.20555	0.02055	0.35461
Kurtosis	17.40933	7.97882	13.92706	8.12052
Jarque-Bera	21415.87*	2571.68*	12303.41*	2753.55*

* significant at 5% level

Unit Root Test: One of the prerequisites for modeling any data using econometric models is that the data series must be stationary in nature. Most of the financial prices tend to be non-stationary at level (price data or log of price data) and stationary at first difference (rates of returns or the first difference of log of prices). So, it is necessary to test for the stationarity of data before using any econometric model. A series that is non-stationary is said to have unit root property, hence it is called the unit root test. Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test is used for testing the stationarity of price and returns series of the variables. The null hypothesis for ADF test is that the data series has unit root or the series is non-stationary. The results of ADF test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Unit Root Test Results

	ADF Test: <i>t</i> - Statistics	
	Level (Price)	First Difference (Returns)
Nifty	-0.793088	-46.55457*
US Dollar	-1.825003	-49.30824*
Gold	-2.345806	-49.57229*
Crude Oil	-1.853724	-54.78910*

* significant at 5% level

It can be seen from Table 3 that all the variables are non-stationary at level, which means the prices of Nifty, Dollar, gold and crude oil exhibit trending pattern. However, the daily rates of returns on all these variables, measured by first difference of log of prices, do not exhibit unit root property. In other words, the daily rates of returns are stationary in nature with a mean reverting behaviour over. Thus, it can be concluded that any further

analysis using econometric models should be done using the daily returns data and not the price data.

Granger Causality: Granger causality test is used to analyse the inter-relationship between economic variables. The test indicates whether the lags of explanatory variables are able to explain the current values of the dependent variable. The test explains the joint significance of the coefficients of the lags of explanatory variable and tests whether the coefficients are all equal to zero. Thus, the null hypotheses for the test is that the lags of explanatory variables jointly do not have an impact on the dependent variables or the explanatory variable does not Granger cause the dependent variable. Pair wise Granger causality test is used in the study and a uniform lag structure of two is used in all models. Since, Granger Causality test requires that the variables used are stationary, the model is developed using the daily rates of returns on Nifty, Dollar, gold and crude oil, which were found to be stationary as per the ADF test. The results of Granger causality test are given in Table 4.

Table 4 shows the pair wise Granger Causality test results in terms of F-statistics and its corresponding probability values. Between Nifty and Dollar, it can be seen that while Nifty Granger causes Dollar, the same is not true in the opposite direction. There is no Granger Causality in either direction as far as the relationship between Nifty and gold is concerned. When it comes to the relationship between Nifty and crude oil, the Granger causality is seen to be flowing from Nifty to crude oil and not in the reverse direction. A similar relation is seen between Dollar and crude oil with the former Granger causing the later and no such causality seen flowing from the later to the former. In case of gold pairing with Dollar and crude oil, it can be seen that gold Granger causes both Dollar and crude, while there is no such causality in the reverse direction.

Table 4: Granger Causality Test

Null Hypothesis	F-Statistic	Probability
Nifty does not Granger Cause US Dollar	76.7185*	0.0000
US Dollar does not Granger Cause Nifty	2.3466	0.0959
Nifty does not Granger Cause Gold	0.6095	0.5437
Gold does not Granger Cause Nifty	0.5354	0.5855
Nifty does not Granger Cause Crude Oil	11.2072*	0.0000
Crude Oil does not Granger Cause Nifty	0.5752	0.5627
US Dollar does not Granger Cause Crude Oil	7.9985*	0.0003
Crude Oil does not Granger Cause US Dollar	0.1570	0.8547
Gold does not Granger Cause US Dollar	16.8076*	0.0000
US Dollar does not Granger Cause Gold	1.7536	0.1734
Gold does not Granger Cause Crude Oil	3.7256*	0.0242
Crude Oil does not Granger Cause Gold	0.0017	0.9983

* significant at 5% level

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Figure 2: Flow of Granger Causality

The Granger causality test does not suggest proof of bi-directional causality between any variables. The significant causality is seen unidirectional flowing from Nifty to Dollar, Nifty to crude oil, Dollar to crude oil, gold to Dollar and gold to crude oil. It is also important to note that Nifty and gold are not being influenced by any other variable, while Dollar is influenced by both Nifty and gold. Granger causality is flowing towards crude from all the other three variables. The flow of causality is presented in Figure 2.

4.1 Analysis and Discussion

The data analysis shows that Nifty and gold have given comparatively better average annual returns (slightly above 10.50% per annum) during the ten year period of 2008-2018. Dollar and crude oil gave only about 5.50% annual returns on an average. While crude oil remained highly volatile followed by Nifty; Dollar exhibited lowest level of volatility. Analysis of daily rates of returns showed similar results as far as the risk of returns, measured in terms of standard deviation, was concerned. Crude showed the highest volatility, with Dollar having the lowest. Nifty and gold remain to be the most sought after investment avenues as they have given decent returns during this period. It is worth noting that the period of 2008-2018 saw many global developments, including the US subprime crisis, which affected the financial markets adversely. In spite of this Nifty and gold have generated reasonable returns during this period. It is also interesting to note that while these two asset classes have moved mostly in opposite directions, on an average, they seem to compensate each other's loss in the long-run as both offered around 10.50% average annual returns over ten year.

The results of Granger Causality throw light on some interesting aspects about the inter-relationship among these markets in India. Though it is believed that stock markets and gold prices are strongly negatively related to each other, no causality seemed to be flowing between the two. While the general perception is that Dollar influences other financial markets, it is found that while causality doesn't flow from Dollar to any other variables, Nifty and gold Granger Cause Dollar in the Indian market. Crude oil returns are found to be Granger Caused by the returns on Nifty, gold as well as Dollar. Nifty and gold emerge as the preferred investment avenues, while those investing on Dollar should be careful about its sensitivity to changes in Nifty and gold prices. Investment

in crude oil should be done with great caution as the crude prices in India are found to be strongly influenced by Nifty, Dollar and gold. Any fluctuations in these markets are expected to affect the price of crude oil.

5. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the stock market as well as commodity market, represented by gold, are performing well. There is no causality between the two. However, the foreign exchange market, represented by US Dollar seems to be influenced by movements in stock market and commodity market. Crude oil, which is a major commodity, is influenced by stock market, foreign exchange market as well as gold, another strong asset in the commodity market. These inter-relationships are important for investors and traders who want to include these asset classes in their portfolio.

6. REFERENCES

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